

PRESS RELEASE

EMERITUS

emeritus

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101073874.

EMERITUS brings new momentum to the fight against environmental crime

Officially launched on the 1st of September 2022, with the first in-presence meeting held on the 4th and 5th of October in Brussels, **EMERITUS** is an innovation project that aims at aggregating advanced technological tools **in a single-entry digital point platform**. This is intended to support Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs) and Border Guards (BGs) in the effective **investigation of environmental crime** at national and cross-border levels, facilitating collaborative operations and networking in this domain. The project “**Environmental crimes’ intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources**” has received funding from the European Union’s [Horizon Europe research and innovation programme](#) (HORIZON-CL3-2021-FCT-01) under grant agreement No. 101073874.

The overall **objective** of this project is to develop a **protocol** for the effective investigation of environmental crimes, integrating the use in operations of **innovative surveillance and analysis technologies** – such as drones, satellite data, virtual sensors, geo-intelligence data, etc. - clustered in a unique digital platform. In order to enable the actual use of such technologies, a complementary **training programme** will be undertaken during the project to foster the intelligence and investigation capabilities of the authorities responsible for enforcing environmental regulations and prosecuting related crimes, combining theoretical aspects and practical simulations. EMERITUS thus aims to explore and demonstrate how these technologies and specialised training could improve the efficiency of environmental crime detection and intelligent risk profiling to optimise resources, reduce the risk for operators and provide a deterrent for offenders.

EMERITUS is executed by a **consortium** of 20 partners, including top-level research institutions, industrial companies, security-specialised SMEs, NGOs, LEAs and BGs, from 9 countries (Austria, Belgium, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom, Romania, and Moldova) plus 3 affiliated entities. The partners will create an active and innovative ecosystem capable of bringing together expertise in technologies applications for criminal investigation, environmental crimes, satellite data and image elaboration, drones, artificial intelligence (AI), training and co-creation, and operative/field investigation.

In addition, the project will rely on the competence and experiences of a network of external stakeholders via a **Community of Practice (CoP)**. The CoP, currently under development, will create a stable community of experts and practitioners that can be informed about the project advancements and results of the EMERITUS project (in advance and more extensively vis-à-vis public communication activities), provide specific feedback and inputs to improve the solutions elaborated, and will establish a specific Policy Maker Board which will lead the definition of policy recommendation and a roadmap to standardise EMERITUS’ results.

To pursue the project’s objective, the consortium will implement **four coordinated workstreams**, encompassing co-creation activities with LEAs, platform technical development, networking and validation in realistic conditions. In particular, the experimentation and validation activities integrated within the training programme will engage LEAs and BGs and technological partners in the implementation of **four** selected highly relevant **use cases**. These concern water contaminant source detection, waste storage centres monitoring, cross-border illegal waste trafficking monitoring and the identification of illegal waste sites.

The project has a duration of 36 months, with the 1st of September 2022 being its start date.

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EMERITUS website: <https://emeritusproject.eu/>

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Sing up for the **EMERITUS Community of Practices (CoP):** <https://emeritusproject.eu/community-practices/>

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Contacts:

Project Coordination Contacts:

Freddy Rivas González

EMERITUS Project Coordinator

Email: coordination@emeritusproject.eu

Margherita Volpe

EMERITUS Project Operative Referent

Email: coordination@emeritusproject.eu

Media Contact

Edoardo Genova

EMERITUS Communication Manager

Email: communication@emeritusproject.eu

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